

HTS-Seg: Heterotypic Tumor Spheroids Segmentation Dataset

Using the Full-Size Images

The full-size images (2160×3840pixels) in this dataset can be used to design and train deep learning models that can handle large input image sizes. These high-resolution images can be useful for tasks such as feature extraction, visual analysis, and developing models that require detailed spatial information.

Using the Segmented Images

The smaller segmented images (512 x 512 pixels) can be used for training and evaluating image segmentation models. These pre-segmented images can help streamline the development process and allow for faster experimentation with different segmentation architectures and techniques.

Analyzing Class Differences

Since the dataset includes two distinct classes, "Control" and "Treatment", you can use the images to analyze the differences between these two groups. This can provide insights into the effects of the treatment on the Heterotypic Tumor Spheroids and help develop more effective therapeutic strategies.

Leveraging the CSV Metadata

The provided CSV file contains additional metadata about the images, including the unique ID assigned to each Heterotypic Tumor Spheroid. This information can be used to study the temporal changes and behavior of individual spheroids, potentially leading to a better understanding of their growth and response to treatment over time.